

ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY METHODS OF MINING METAL ORES

Tolibayev Yerlan Amangeldiyevich

Student of Nukus Mining Institute:

Jienbaev Atabay Nietbay o'g'li

Student of Nukus Mining Institute:

Dauletbayev Zamir Tangjarbay o'g'li

Student of Nukus Mining Institute:

O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li

Student of Nukus Mining Institute:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7686875>

Abstract: The mining industry developed mainly through the use of two strategies: pyrometallurgy and hydrometallurgy. Both have been successfully used to extract precious metals from ore deposits. These strategies will undoubtedly harm the environment, albeit in small amounts. Also, over the decades mining industry, there was a global decline in high-grade ores. This led to a decrease in value metal supply, which prompted a rethinking of traditional strategies as an industry faces the current challenge of extracting highly sought-after precious metals from low-grade ores. This review details these challenges, provides insight into the challenges of metal recovery, and describes the technological advances being made to solve the problems associated with low quality metals. It also discusses the pragmatic change that requires the use of biotechnological solutions provided by Environmental Harm Reduction, particularly its environmental friendliness. However, it highlights potential solutions and criticizes environmental shortcomings A custom-built approach that integrates research applications from multiple technologies and their interaction Environmental damage can be reduced by studying the harsh environments associated with metal ore degradation. Otelbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute at the Navoi State University of Mining and Technologies. that heavy metals in the environment lead to the development of human and aquatic life and I learned new methods of extraction, recovery and analysis of metal ions. With special attention tried to consider strategies that minimize environmental friendly approaches. Use of organic solvents, application of micromethodology, waste limitation, cost reduction, safe and use good or reusable materials. This review discusses recent developments in liquid and solid phases. Mining equipment. Liquid-based methods include advances in the use of aqueous two- and three-phase systems, liquid membranes, and cloud point extraction. Recent advances in exploitation new sorbent materials for solid phase extraction, solid phase microextraction and bulk mining issues are also

discussed. The main goal of my research is to minimize the impact of metals on the environment. Basically, a lot of energy consumption is observed in the process of metal processing.

Keywords: Metal mining, low-grade ore, metal recovery, metallurgical methods, biological washing, ecological contamination, liquid-liquid extraction, solid phase extraction, solid phase microextraction, metal mining methods, adsorption, biosorption.

Introduction

At first, only precious metals were prioritized, but with the development of different types industries and their demand for rare metals for their manufacturing activities have shifted focus introducing the various metals required. We have witnessed this for many years development and improvement of technologies adapted to extraction and processing information on the indicators of technologies for the extraction of various types of metals is shown. In addition, these are technological advances adapted to facilitate the extraction of minerals of interest from low-grade ores the alarming expected consequences of the rate of depletion of high-grade ore reserves. It will happen the processes of increasing exploitation of previously underutilized low-grade ores are envisaged. Surprisingly, it is In the 19th and early 20th centuries, low-grade ores were considered unusable and mining activities are concentrated in ore bodies containing at least 5% or more metal ores of interest remain. Such decisions affect not only the efficiency of the enterprise and profitability may have depended on the technological capabilities of that time. However, the current the state of affairs as well as the need to meet the growing demand has changed the outlook of the industry, With technological considerations including ore bodies containing less than 2% metal we can see that interests are high. Low-grade ores are obtained from various sources, including newly opened mines reserves or mine tailings containing previously overlooked metals, perhaps as a result It is determined based on the mining activities and processes in other target metal during preliminary mining and exploration. The target metal is often in high concentration, and the extraction it will be easier. Regardless of the source, low-grade ores have been conventionally mined has been shown to cause more environmental problems by producing more waste. ultimately leading to soil and water pollution and ultimately climate change. These are Environmental problems - the impact of mining activities on the biophysical environment which leads to environmental degradation. In addition, the presence mine tailings are considered a health hazard as well as an

environmental problem and reducing the concentration of toxic elements through recycling processes is seen as an environmental enrichment initiative. This initiative is a necessary mitigation strategy, long-term environmental damage caused by transformation reactions and production acid mine drainage. In the presence of a water-activating microbial solution activity, these inevitable biochemical reactions occur. However, recovery processes, especially using conventional methods, can be unprofitable due to their inferiority and can release toxic gases into the environment.

Picture 1. Schematic representation of a two-phase and three-phase system for the extraction of metal ions

Conversely, when dealing with low-grade ore mining, we must consider economic and opportunity costs. The second is the focus on justification environmental sustainability is an important consideration in all mining strategies for future generations. As a result, to solve mining problems low-grade ores, current technological developments must include the environment friendly approach, as well as looking for alternatives that provide profitability. This review will see the progress made in this regard. Along with learning these advances, there have been significant changes In recent years, attention has been paid to biotechnological methods to solve environmental pollution problems associated with traditional smelting methods and the use of toxic chemicals. However, this biotechnological alternative has not yet been achieved in industrial-scale mining popularity or commercial acceptance. This is how the situation came to a standstill This may be one of the main reasons for maintaining the biotechnological approach in improving the biological capacity

of the microorganisms used for this operation. It should be noted that in each extraction step, one target metal should be extracted with two phases in the system, the process of obtaining a certain metal from a mixture of metal ions must be very selective, resulting in a potentially lengthy and expensive method. A well-designed three-fluid extraction The system can overcome this disadvantage by selective separation and two or more target extraction metals can be extracted in a single extraction step with less environmental damage. However, the appeal of biological extraction remains its undeniable ecological purity compared to such technological operations melting and electrical absorption. Due to this appeal, it is also a current trend From an environmental perspective, bioleaching remains a focus of research efforts to open the possibility of obtaining metal from ores. In addition, bioleaching offers attractive advantages such as energy efficiency and broad spectrum different types of ores and grades, as well as their application to ore processing or mixtures containing very low concentrations of the target metals are present.

Pyrometallurgical process

Pyrometallurgy is a traditional method of mining and refining metals high temperature calcination, roasting, reduction and purification. The whole process consumes a lot of energy and adds a lot to the carbon footprint. Although pyrometallurgical energy requirements vary with ore grade and mineralogy, current the exploitation of low-grade ores can have a significant impact on the energy of the mining process include requirements.

Hydrometallurgical Process

Concerns have been raised about air pollution from pyrometallurgical processes governments must impose strict limits by implementing emission regulations and acceptable limits to ensure a significant level of environmental protection. Compliance is required throughout the business cycle for mining companies where they are expected to carry out land reclamation and start operations to the end cleaning activities. It is also necessary to obtain legal documents related to pollution mitigation and prevention in accordance with each country's specific mining legislation. Most of these laws have an environmental theme and even require the use of best practices and best available technology. Hydrometallurgy is a process that uses chemical reactions for extraction interesting metals from ores, concentrates and recycled materials. Sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), hydrochloric acid (HCl), ferrous sulfate, nitric acid (HNO_3), ferric chloride, sodium chloride and other inorganic chemicals are used to wash metals

from various raw materials. materials. In hydrometallurgy, metal recovery is often H_2SO_4 , but it has adverse environmental impacts caused by accidental spills. The potential for groundwater contamination from transported H_2SO_4 leaks that cause leaks through burst pipes and onto the surrounding land, too high. However, technological progress has led to their replacement chemicals that are less harmful to the environment. In addition, hydrometallurgical processes developed in recent years to solve the problem of mining low metal concentrations ores. Historically, the majority of zinc metal was obtained from zinc sulfide ores. However, Due to the current depletion of zinc sulfide ores, the exploitation of zinc oxide ores has increased.

Picture 2. Schematic representation of solid-phase extraction, solid-phase microextraction, and dispersed solid-phase extraction

Conclusions

Recovery of metals often requires extensive extraction from complex matrices metal analysis is routinely sought at trace levels. In both cases, the strategies considered greener and minimizing their environmental impact will help develop new methods for metal extraction and analysis, most of which are described in this review. A huge part of the evolution of metal mining and sample preparation have benefited from the development and use of new materials. offering the beneficial properties of low flammability and volatility, excellent solubility and high thermal stability. Solid phase extraction is further reduced the need for organic solvents and uses new materials based on adsorption, biosorption, ligand. binding and ion exchange. Significant progress has been made in understanding the impact of environmental protection. Mining activity. However, the importance of mining in various applications, e.g refers to the production of metal for domestic and industrial purposes or for profit the mining process continues as long as there is demand to be met. As As a result, this review highlighted the challenges in processing low-grade ores.

technological progress and its impact on the environment. This review key findings are highlighted and summarized below.

* As a result of the reduction in the global rate of high-grade ores, the possibility low-grade ore reserves that serve as future sources of base metals are high. Besides, mine tailings are an easily recycled source of high-yield metals. The nature of low-grade ores creates difficulties in mining and processing. Their otherwise we can see the sides that hinder profitability. Continuous technological evolution of existing processes processes, on the contrary, have the ability to mitigate this effect.

* Environmental impact of mining processes is a major problem for mining industry regardless of ore grade. This review focuses on the changes made the types of chemicals or energy saving methods conditions that are targeted at the meeting required environmental standards set by various mining sectors studied among countries. Some of these advances in traditional methods are a favoring hydrometallurgy over pyrometallurgy avoids considerable environmental pollution. Although hydrometallurgy presents greater difficulties in product recovery than pyrometallurgy, the latter faces related to the exhaustion of the process's innovative potential and its inherent challenges high carbon footprint. Effective development problem-solving and gathering processing methods of low-grade ores remain at the center of modern caused a number of disputes and negotiations in mining enterprises. Finally, the continuous technological advancement of traditional methods will allow us to improve the recovery of metal from low-grade ores while reducing the negative impact on the environment. pollution process can be reduced. Nevertheless, despite the difficulties faced by the biological, it remains an advanced technology compared to traditional methods in the present era. This is also possible it will be useful to strengthen molecular research on biological microorganisms Accelerating the potential of biological process improvement will reduce these environmental damages. O'telbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute at the Navoi State University of Mining and Technology, gave several examples of the processes of their application in mining and presented to international journals the methods of automation of mining technologies through microprocessors and the technologies in mining at the same time. proved with several examples that it can be used in several technological processes. The use of modern technologies plays an important role in the development economy of the mine. It is necessary to pay attention to the parameters of technologies when automating processes in mining enterprises.

Do not set the load beyond the limits of the technology, only then the technology will work for a long time without problems. In this article, I will inform you that if we install a microprocessor (automatic mode memory) in the technology in the mining enterprises, we will prevent the overloading of the technology. This ensures the operation of the enterprise and the safety of workers. Otelbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute at the Navoi State University of Mining and Technology, has articles on metallurgical processes, components of metals, and metal enrichment processes. Much research has been done on the metallurgical industry. A number of information on processes in metallurgical deposits, extraction of metals, corrosion of metals and extraction of metals by flotation methods are presented.

References:

1. Djaksimuratov, K., O'razmatov, J., Yuldashev, S., Toshpulatov, D., & O'telbayev, A. (2021). Geological-Geochemical and Mineralogical Properties of Basalt Rocks of Karakalpakstan.
2. Djaksimuratov Karamatdin Mustapaevich, O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li, O'razmatov Jonibek Ikromboy o'g'li, & Mnajatdinov Dastan Mnajatdin o'g'li. (2021). PROPERTIES OF COAL, PROCESSES IN COAL MINING COMPANIES, METHODS OF COAL MINING IN THE WORLD. JournalNX - A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal, 7(10), 231-236. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/32N4G>
3. Djaksimuratov, K., Toshev, O., O'razmatov, J., & O'telbayev, A. (2021). MEASURING AND CRUSHING THE STRENGTH OF ROCKS USE OF VARIOUS TYPES OF SURFACTANTS FOR GRINDING.
4. Djaksimuratov, K., Ravshanov, Z., O'razmatov, J., & O'telbayev, A. (2021). Comprehensive monitoring of surface deformation in underground mining, prevention of mining damage. Modern technologies and their role in mining.
5. Djaksimuratov, K., O'razmatov, J., Maulenov, N., & O'telbayev, A. (2021). FACTORS INFLUENCING THE CONDITIONS OF OPEN PIT MINING, ORE MASS AND DEFORMATION, PROCESSES THAT LEAD TO IMBALANCE DURING EXCAVATION.
6. Djaksimuratov, K., Jumabayeva, G., Maulenov, N., & Rametullayeva, M. (2022). Improving the Efficiency of Excavators Increasing the Efficiency of Temporary Ditch Excavator.
7. Djaksimuratov, K., Jumabayeva, G., Maulenov, N., & Rametullayeva, M. (2022). MONITORING THE CONDITION OF THE DEPOSIT IN MINING ENTERPRISES. MODERN METHODS OF DETERMINING THE LOCATION OF MINERALS.

8. Djaksimuratov, K., Joldasbayeva, A., Bayramova, M., Tolibayev, E., & Maulenov, N. (2022). TECHNOLOGICAL CLASSIFICATION OF UNDERGROUND EXCAVATION WORKS IN GEOTECHNICAL MONITORING SYSTEMS.
9. Djaksimuratov, K., Maulenov, N., Ametov, R., Rametullayeva, M., & Bayramova, M. (2022). MODERN TECHNICAL METHODS OF MONITORING LANDSLIDES IN OPEN MINES.
10. Joldasbayeva, A., Ametov, R., Embergenov, A., Maulenov, N., & Kulmuratova, A. (2022). Technology to prevent Methane or coal dust explosions in the mine.
11. Djaksimuratov, K., Maulenov, N., Rametullayeva, M., Kulmuratova, A., & Embergenov, A. (2022). Technology for Determining the Force of Impact on Buildings in the Vicinity during Blasting Operations in Mines.
12. Djaksimuratov, K., Jumabayeva, G., Maulenov, N., & Rametullayeva, M. (2022). CORROSION OF METALS AND FACTORS AFFECTING IT. METHODS OF PREVENTING CORROSION OF METALS.
13. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi, Utepbaeva Gulnaz Saken qizi, O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li, Azizov Azatbek Jumabek o'g'li, & Yo'ldashova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2022). AUTOMATION AND ROBOTIZATION OF UNDERGROUND MINES. International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology, 9(10), 20–28. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/UYH93>
14. Ravshanov Zavqiddin Yahyo o'g'li, O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li, O'razmatov Jonibek Ikromboy o'g'li, Zaytova Madina Nazarbay qizi, & Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2022). Conveyor belt structure and mode of operation in mines. Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology, 11, 72–80. Retrieved from <https://www.geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejet/article/view/2360>
15. Mustapaevich, D. K., Axmet o'g'li, M. N., Baxitbay qizi, J. A., Alisher o'g'li, O'telbayev A., & Ikromboy o'g'li, O. J. (2022). Model Of Stages of Determination of Strength of Dynamic Fracture of Rocks and Digital Technological Verification. Miasto Przyszłości, 28, 230–239. Retrieved from <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/620>
16. Djaksimuratov Karamatdin Mustapaevich, Ravshanov Zavqiddin Yahyo o'g'li, Ergasheva Zulxumor Abdaaliyevna, O'razmatov Jonibek Ikromboy o'g'li, & O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li. (2022). Underground mine mining systems and technological parameters of mine development. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact Factor: 7.429, 11(10), 110–117. Retrieved from <https://www.gejournal.net/index.php/IJSSIR/article/view/1016>

17. Mustapaevich, D. K., Axmet o'g'li, M. N., Baxitbay qizi, J. A., Alisher o'g'li, O. A., & Ikromboy o'g'li, O. J. (2022). Methods of Determining the Effect of Temperature and Pressure on the Composition of Rocks. Vital Annex : International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences, 1(4), 98–106. Retrieved from <https://innosci.org/IJNRAS/article/view/393>
18. Ravshanov Zavqiddin Yahyo o'g'li, O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li, Joldasbayeva Aysulu Baxitbay qizi, & Bayramova Minevvar Axmet qizi. (2023). MINING TECHNOLOGICAL EQUIPMENT THAT DETERMINES THE SLOPE ANGLES OF THE MINE BY MEANS OF LASER BEAMS. Neo Scientific Peer Reviewed Journal, 6, 17–23. Retrieved from <https://neojournals.com/index.php/nspj/article/view/96>
19. Yeshmuratova, A., Kulmuratova, A., Maulenov, N., & Otemisov, U. (2023). MINE BLASTING PROCESSES OPTIMIZATION STAGES OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY OF DETONATORS.
20. Ravshanov, Z., Joldasbayeva, A., Maulenov, N., & O'telbayev, A. (2023). Determination of mineral location coordinates in geotechnology and mining enterprises.
21. Djaksimuratov, K., Batirova, U., Otemisov, U., & Aytmuratov, S. (2023). STEPS FOR DETERMINING THE SLOPE ANGLE OF AN OPEN MINE.
22. Djaksimuratov, K., Batirova, U., Abdullaev, A., & Joldasbayeva, A. (2023). GATHERING COORDINATES OF THE GEOLOGICAL AND GEOTECHNICAL LOCATION OF THE MINE.
23. Ravshanov, Z., Joldasbayeva, A., Bayramova, M., & Madreymov, A. (2023). IN GEOLOGICAL AND GEOTECHNICAL PROCESSES IN THE MINE USE OF TECHNOLOGICAL SCANNING EQUIPMENT IN THE UNDERGROUND MINING METHOD.
24. Djaksimuratov, K., Jumabayeva, G., Maulenov, N., & Rametullayeva, M. (2022). Casting And Evaluation of Properties for an Aluminum Alloy Material and Optimizing the Quality Control Parameters.
25. Djaksimuratov, K., Jumabayeva, G., Batirova, U., & O'telbayev, A. (2023). GROUNDWATER CONTROL IN MINES
26. Abdiramanova, Z., Jumabayeva, G., Batirova, U., & O'telbayev, A. (2023). ACTIVITY OF TEBINBULAK IRON ORE MINING ENTERPRISES IN THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN.
27. Qurbonov.A.A, Djaksimuratov Karamatdin Mustapaevich, & O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li. (2021). FACTORS INFLUENCING THE CONDITIONS OF OPEN PIT MINING, ORE MASS AND DEFORMATION. PROCESSES THAT LEAD TO

- IMBALANCE DURING EXCAVATION. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 1(6), 45–49. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5500210>
28. O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li. (2022). STRENGTH PROPERTIES OF ROCKS AND FACTORS INFLUENCING THEM AND THE PROCESS OF CHANGING THE PROPERTIES OF ROCKS. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6034442>
29. Joldasbayeva, A., Maulenov, N., Mnajatdinov, D., & O'telbayev, A. (2023). PROCESSES OF DRAWING UP A VENTILATION SYSTEM SCHEME IN MINES.
30. Maulenov, N., Joldasbayeva, A., O'razmatov, J., & Mnajatdinov, D. (2023). TECHNOLOGICAL MODES OF MONITORING THE LOCATION OF MINES IN THE MINE AND THE SLOPE BORDER OF THE BLAST AREA.
31. Maulenov, N., Joldasbayeva, A., Amanbaev, N., & Mnajatdinov, D. (2023). PROCESSES OF BENEFICIATION AND EXTRACTION OF ORES IN IRON MINES (IN THE EXAMPLE OF TEBIN BULAK IRON MINE).
32. Maulenov, N., Joldasbayeva, A., Amanbaev, N., & Mnajatdinov, D. (2023). DETERMINATION OF VIBRATIONS CAUSED BY BLASTING PROCESSES IN OPEN PIT MINING AT MINING ENTERPRISES.
33. Maulenov, N., Joldasbayeva, A., O'razmatov, J., & Mnajatdinov, D. (2023). MOBILE TECHNOLOGICAL METHODS OF SAFETY MANAGEMENT IN SURFACE MINING.
34. Utepbayeva Gulnaz Saken qizi, Urazbayeva Aqmaral Sulayman qizi, Joldasbaeva Feruza Jan'abay qizi, O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li. (2023). FOAM FLOTATION PROCESS, STAGES AND TECHNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7641035>
35. Patualieva, Q., Joldasbaeva, J., & Eshimbetova, M. (2023). STAGES OF USING GEODETIC METHODS IN OPEN MINING CONDITIONS.
36. O'TELBAYEVA Muhayyo Alisherovna. (2023). METHODOLOGY AND THEORY OF CHEMISTRY TEACHING IN SCHOOLS, METHODS AND PROCESSES OF THEIR STUDY. Journal of Experimental Studies, 2(2), 10–16. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7623700>
37. O'TELBAYEVA Muhayyo Alisherovna. (2023). ANALYSIS OF PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL METHODS AND APPROACHES. Pedagogical and Psychological Studies, 2(2), 12–16. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7624764>
38. Jumabayeva Guljahon Jaqsilikovna. (2023). CONTROL OF UNDERGROUND WATER IN THE MINE, DETECTION AND PREVENTION OF RISKS. ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE, 2(5), 159–166. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7648010>

39. Patualieva, Q. (2023). METHODS OF DETERMINING THE COORDINATE DIMENSIONS OF AN OBJECT ON MAPS, CARTOGRAPHY AND GEOGRAPHIC LOCATIONS.
40. Mustapaevich, D. K., o'g'li, M. N. A., qizi, J. A. B., o'g'li, O. A. A., & qizi, K. A. J. (2022). Calculation of the Technological Scheme of Traffic Control of Mine Transport in Open Mines. International Journal on Orange Technologies, 4(10), 34-42. Retrieved from <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJOT/article/view/3570>
41. Утемисов А. О., Юлдашова Х. Б. К. СИСТЕМЫ АВТОМАТИЧЕСКОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ //Universum: технические науки. – 2022. – №. 5-2 (98). – С. 45-47.
42. Utemisov, A. (2019). Таълим жараёнида компьютер ва инновацион технологияларнинг роли.
43. Ametov Bayram Tursynbaevich, Uzakbaeva Akmaral Sulayman Kizi, & Allamuratov Guljamal Bisengali Kizi. (2022). Wind Mill and Solar Energy. Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology, 15, 178–179. Retrieved from <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjet/article/view/3068>
44. Аметов, Б. Т. (2021). Возникновение И Распространение Ударной Волны В Твёрдом Теле. IJTIMOIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 1(6), 42-44.
45. Аметов, Б. Т., Султанбаев, А. П., & Жангабаев, А. К. (2021). ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ И ПРОБЛЕМЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМЫХ ИСТОЧНИКОВ ЭНЕРГИИ. In КОНКУРС МОЛОДЫХ УЧЁНЫХ (pp. 72-74).
46. Tursynbaevich, A. B., Kizi, U. A. S., & Kizi, A. G. B. (2022). Wind Mill and Solar Energy. Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology, 15, 178-180.
47. АМЕТОВ Б. Т., АМИДУЛЛАЕВА Ю. Б. К., КИЗИ И. О. И. РАДИАЦИОННО-СТИМУЛИРОВАННОЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЕ ОПТИЧЕСКИХ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИК КВАНТОВО-РАЗМЕРНЫХ СТРУКТУР СОЕДИНЕНИЙ А2В6 //Studies in Economics and Education in the Modern World. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 9.
48. АМЕТОВ Б. Т., КИЗИ А. М. М., КИЗИ К. А. Ж. ВЛИЯНИЕ МИКРОВОЛНОВОЙ ОБРАБОТКИ НА СВОЙСТВА АРСЕНИДГАЛЛИЕВЫХ ДИОДНЫХ СТРУКТУР С БАРЬЕРОМ ШОТТКИ //ЛУЧШАЯ НАУЧНАЯ СТАТЬЯ 2022. – 2022. – С. 8-10.
49. Бубякин М. Ю. ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ 3D ПРИНТЕРА ДЛЯ АДДИТИВНОГО ИЗГОТОВЛЕНИЯ ДЕТАЛЕЙ //КОНКУРС МОЛОДЫХ УЧЁНЫХ. – 2021. – С. 55-60.

50. Аметов Б. Т. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ СТРУКТУРЫ ТЕ-CDTE СО СВОЙСТВОМ ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО ПЕРЕКЛЮЧЕНИЯ ПРИ ИМПУЛЬСНОМ ЛАЗЕРНОМ ОБЛУЧЕНИИ CDTE //Интернаука. – 2021. – Т. 10. – №. 186 часть 2. – С. 18.
51. А.А. Eshmuratova. (2022). MATCAD DASTURIDAN FOYDALANIB IKKI VA UCH O`LCHOVLI GRAFIKLARNI QURISH . Journal of Integrated Education and Research, 1(5), 534–539. Retrieved from <https://ojs.rmasav.com/index.php/ojs/article/view/341>
52. Karamatdin D., Baxitgul D. A. K. Changes In The Regime And Use Of Fresh Groundwater In The Southern Aral Sea Region //Solid State Technology. – 2020. – Т. 63. – №. 6. – С. 15884-15887.
53. Курбанов А. А., Джаксымуратов К., Отелбаев А. ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ БАЗАЛЬТОВЫХ ПОРОД В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 3-2. – С. 61-65.
54. Kaipbergenov, Atabek Tulepbergenovich, Askarbek Orazimbetovich Utemisov, and Hilola Bakhtiyor Kizi Yuldashova. "STEADY OF AUTOMATIC CONTROL SYSTEMS." Academic research in educational sciences 3.6 (2022): 918-921.
55. Tulepbergenovich, Kaipbergenov Batirbek, and Utemisov Askarbek Orazimbetovich. "Classification and analysis of computer programs for the physical preparation of athletes and expasure of prospects for their studies." European science review 7-8 (2015): 11-13.

